

Machine Learning System Requirements Specification

Switch account

* Required

Email *

Your email

What is your name? *

Your answer

Perspectives and concerns of specifying ML-enabled systems

1. In your opinion, what is the relevance of each perspective for specifying ML systems? *

	Little Relevant	Very Relevant
ML objectives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
User Experience	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2. In your opinion, are the concerns of each perspective complete? *
For those who select the 'No' option, indicate what is missing, in your opinion, in the next question.

	Yes	No
ML objectives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
User Experience	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

For the perspectives that you rated "No" in the previous question, please indicate unaddressed concerns.

Your answer

Do you have any other suggestions for improvements related to the perspectives and concerns?

Your answer

3. Regarding your perception of the ease of use, usefulness and intention to use the specification document, how much do you agree with the following statements: *

	Strongly disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Strongly agree
I found the approach easy to use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using the approach would be useful to support more complete and accurate specification of ML-based system requirements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would use the approach to specify ML-based system requirements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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